

Can a massive star possess its own planetary system?

Vito Squicciarini

Department of Physics and Astronomy 'Galileo Galilei', University of Padova, Vicolo dell'Osservatorio 3, 35122, Padova, Italy

INAF - Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo dell'Osservatorio 5, 35122, Padova, Italy

Having recently reached the impressive milestone of 5000 confirmed exoplanets, the exoplanetary field has attained in less than 30 years a remarkable degree of maturity. Not only is a purely discovery phase giving way to a more thorough characterization phase, but also the quest for statistical trends connecting the observed properties of the exoplanet population has rapidly become a major scientific goal. Unveiling the physical processes lurking behind the multifaceted hues of observed planetary architectures –and the limits outside which these processes no longer work– is indeed the ultimate purpose of *exoplanet demographics*.

Figure 1: Mass vs semimajor axis of confirmed exoplanets. Only exoplanets whose stellar host mass is known to a precision of at least 30% are shown. Each planet is labeled according to its detection method: transits in red, radial velocity in green, microlensing in orange and direct imaging in blue. Source: NASA Exoplanet Archive.

Is the exoplanet census unbiased?

The foundations of exoplanet demographics lie in a powerful, yet simple idea: namely, that the distribution of exoplanets as a function of their physical, orbital and stellar-host properties has been thoroughly crafted by physical processes related to their formation and subsequent evolution. However, these trends are mostly concealed by detection biases intrinsic to the detection techniques employed. In other words, each method has its strengths and weaknesses, and is suited to probing only a specific portion of the parameter space (Figure 1).

As a consequence of the bias of transits and radial velocities (RV) for closed-in planets, about 90% of the confirmed exoplanets lie closer to their stars than the Earth is to the Sun. Moreover, 99.3% of the confirmed

exoplanets orbit around stars with $M_* < 2M_\odot$; given that about 96% of the stars have $M_* < 2M_\odot$, *high-mass* stars ($M_* > 2M_\odot$) are underrepresented by a factor of six. Is it just a sensitivity problem, or is there any physical obstacle that makes it difficult –and eventually impossible– to form a planet around a star of increasing mass?

The impact of stellar mass

The occurrence of giant planets (which are the easiest to detect) as a function of the stellar host mass has been the focus of several radial velocities campaigns. A robust positive correlation between giant planet occurrence and stellar mass exists [1]; however, after reaching a peak at $M_* \approx 1.7M_\odot$, a turnoff is observed in this occurrence, eventually dropping to 0% at $M_* \gtrsim 3M_\odot$. A peak in the semimajor axis distribution at a few au and a significant positive correlation with stellar metallicity are also observed.

These trends are in line with the predictions of core accretion (CA), the mechanism thought to be responsible of giant planet formation in our solar system [2]. The increased reservoir of disk mass –scaling with stellar mass– is naturally reflected into a greater frequency of gas giants, and the increasingly rapid dispersal of the protoplanetary disk around heavier stars eventually leaves not enough time for giant planet formation at $M_* \gtrsim 3M_\odot$.

However, the sensitivity of RV gradually degrades with orbital distance, and it can be shown that for $M_* \gtrsim 2.5M_\odot$ the technique gets essentially blind to the region where giant planet formation should preferentially take place [3]. This is extremely important, as RV is even blinder to the wide-orbit exoplanet population possibly produced by a different mechanism, gravitational instability (GI) [4]. Unlike CA, GI preferentially creates a flat mass distribution of Super Jupiters and brown dwarfs at wide separations from their stars. Extending the demographics of giant planets to this regime would help clarifying the relative weight of the two contributions; direct imaging, a technique that is preferentially sensitive to young giant planets in wide orbits, is particularly suited to this scope.

The BEAST survey

The direct-imaging B-star Exoplanet Abundance Study (BEAST) is the first planet-hunting survey dedicated to B stars ($M_* > 2.4M_\odot$) [5]. BEAST exploits the high-contrast imaging capabilities of SPHERE@VLT, and in particular those of the Integral Field Spectrograph (IFS) and the dual-band imager (IRDIS), providing images in a $1.7'' \times 1.7''$ and $11 \times 11''$ field of view, respectively.

The stellar sample of BEAST is constituted by 85 members of the Scorpius-Centaurus association, the nearest ($\sim 100 - 200$ pc) star-forming region to the Sun. Binary stars have been retained –with the exception of those in the separation range $0.1 - 6''$, negatively affecting the performance of SPHERE–, offering thus the additional opportunity to investigate the effect of stellar multiplicity. The combination of short distance and young ($\sim 5 - 20$ Myr) age makes this sample particularly suited for direct imaging, enabling the detection of companions as small as $5M_J$.

While the survey is still in progress ($\sim 30\%$ in April 2022), its provisional results are already intriguing. b Cen is a tight binary system, with a total mass of $6 - 10M_\odot$, possessing a $10.9 \pm 1.6M_J$ giant planet at a very wide (~ 550 au) separation [6]. With two observations at hand, plus a serendipitous archival epoch from 2000, we were able to assess the common proper motion to b Cen with $> 7\sigma$ significance.

This object acquires its greatest significance when coupled to a second, even more intriguing detection. μ^2 Sco [7] is, from a stellar evolution standpoint, a massive star ($M = 9.1 \pm 0.3M_\odot$): a star massive enough to end its life as a supernova. A comoving substellar companion, μ^2 Sco b, was found at 290 au (Figure 2). With a mass $M = 14.4 \pm 0.8M_J$, it is slightly above the deuterium-burning limit, which classically marks the transition between planets and brown dwarfs. En passant we mention that, lurking beneath the glaring light of the star, a second candidate was tentatively spotted at an extremely small separation ($0.12'' \approx 20$ au). If confirmed, its luminosity would correspond to that of an object with $M = 18.5 \pm 1.5M_J$.

Figure 2: An image of μ^2 Sco. The star, artificially obscured by the coronagraph, is at the center of the image. Several background sources can be seen as bright point sources. μ^2 Sco b is the source inside the white circle.

Discussion

The nature of these unusual objects is uncertain, and challenges our current view of planet formation. A mass criterion would place b Cen b in the planetary regime and μ^2 Sco b in the brown dwarf regime, but their similar properties strongly argue for classifying them within a unified frame. With respect to their mass ratio q , i.e. the ratio between companion and stellar mass, their $q = 0.001 - 0.002$ are intriguingly similar to that of Jupiter.

Such a q is typical of a core accretion scenario, and an extrapolation of known frequencies of giant planets to the B-star regime is indeed favoured over an extrapolation to low q of the stellar companion distribution [7]. However, the expected timescale of core buildup is of the order of a few million years, much higher than the timescale of disk dissipation ($\sim 10^5$ yr), hence posing an insuperable obstacle to this scenario.

On the other hand, formation timescales are not a problem for the extremely rapid ($10^3 - 10^4$ yr) GI; the large observed orbital separations are naturally consistent with this scenario. However, the mass distribution of GI objects is rather flat, with more than 90% of the objects having masses above the deuterium-burning limit already around $1M_\odot$ stars [8]. Thus, the conversion efficiency of disk mass into companion mass would here be atypically low.

The BEAST survey has already shown that a massive star can possess its own planetary –or at least planet-like– system, challenging our prior views of giant planet formation under such exotic conditions. In the next few years, we will know how frequent these systems are, and thorough follow-up efforts will hopefully shed light on their elusive origin.

References

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Short CV

2013–2017: BSc in Physics, University of Padova, Italy
 2017–2019: MSc in Astronomy, University of Padova, Italy
 2019–present: PhD in Astronomy, University of Padova / INAF, Italy